

REASONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF ENGLISH TO ALL SPHERES IN UZBEKISTAN

G. Muminova

Student FerSU

SH. Maxammadjonova

Teacher FerSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7442661>

Abstract. *In this article, the attention to the English language is growing in Uzbekistan and what opportunities are being opened by the government for youngsters to learn the language through many examples.*

Keywords: *C1 level, IT(informalormation technologies), IELTS certificate, scholarship, textbooks, digital libraries, youngsters.*

ПРИЧИНЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ВО ВСЕ СФЕРЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *В этой статье написано внимание к английскому языку в Узбекистане растет, и на многих примерах какие возможности правительство открывает для молодежи для изучения языка.*

Ключевые слова: *C1 уровень, ИТ(информационные технологии), IELTS сертификат, гранты, учебники, электронные библиотеки, молодежь.*

Nowadays the issue of teaching English to all layers of the society is brought to the main place by our government. As the basis of this policy, we can see that the following tasks have been determined by the President's decision in order to increase the level of mastering of foreign languages by civil servants and to fill state bodies with highly qualified and competitive personal:

Starting from July 1,2021, the practice of training employee in a foreign language at least once a week by engaging teachers of educational organizations on the basis of a contract;

Starting from January 1,2022, employees of all levels of government agencies with national and international certificates in foreign languages will be paid an additional bonus of up to 20 compared to the position salary at the expense of budget funds of organizations outside the budget and within the salary fund.

In addition, foreign language (English, French, German, Spanish, Italian, Arabic, Chinese, Japanese, Korean, Turkish, Persian, Pashto) with at least C1 level national or equivalent internationally recognized certificate of educational institutions, teachers will be paid an additional monthly bonus of 50 percent compared to their base rate.

I believe that the main reason for this is that the English language has become the language used in scientific work and in various negotiations on global scale.

What opportunities does English offer to youngsters?

Most Uzbek youngsters are growing more and more interested in learning English, a new trend that some researchers say is a sign of Uzbekistan's desire to be closer to the United States and western Europe. The graduates of any Uzbek educational institution up to the university level must be proficient in at least two foreign languages, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev announced in May 2022

The requirement stemmed from Mirziyoyev's belief that the country can become competitive on the global market. Starting in 2022, all government agencies will require new hires to know at least one foreign language. The requirement also applies to current workers in government agencies who want a promotion.

As part of the effect, the government has selected 10 languages expected to raise the competitiveness of Uzbek citizens and of the country more generally. English is at the top of the list, followed by Russian, German, French, Chinese, Korean, Japanese, Turkish, Arabic and Farsi. Uzbek is the official language of Uzbekistan, while Russian is the second most widely spoken language, especially in capital and large cities.

However, English is increasing in popularity among youth. Although the country has no public schools with a purely English curriculum, English language courses are popular. Nevertheless, they do not come cheap. For instance, in Tashkent, one learning center charges between \$180 and \$200 (1.9 million UZS to 2.2 million UZS) for a three-month course. In contrast, the minimum monthly wage in Uzbekistan is just 822,000 UZS, about \$80.

Despite the fact that these courses are expensive, many young people do not stop learning. According to statistics, as result of the popularization of the IT industry, the demand for this language is increasing day by day. Also, many opportunities are opening for youngsters who have IELTS certificate. For example, students or applicants with B1, C1 and higher levels are winning scholarships to study abroad. Khusanboy Goyibberdiyev, who was born in 2004 in Bagdad district, Fergana region, is a good example. Currently, he studies at one of the top ranked universities in the USA. His interest in mathematics and, of course, the C1 level from IELTS greatly contributed to his success. Today, young people like him can be found in any region of Uzbekistan. I think the main reason for this is the English language.

What is the government doing to improve the English language?

Mokhira Jamolova, 33, an English teacher for grades one through eight in Bagdad district, says that there is huge interest in studying English. "I am proud that some of my students were able to earn IELTS certificates. To improve our teaching, we need new foreign method, textbooks, and new educational technologies. We need help from American and British teachers," Jamolova said. Jamolova who herself dreams of spending time in the United States to improve her English and share best practices with her foreign counterparts, considers it important to create a permanent system to improve the qualifications of English teachers in Uzbekistan.

"We need to improve training programmes and retrain educators so we do not repeat the situation we were in during the Soviet years." said Bakhrom Rajabov, a political economist in Tashkent. Thus the government concentrate on English teachers' skills.

In these days, 650 Americans have established centers in 150 countries around the world that provide many opportunities, such as English language lessons, computer technology lessons and digital libraries. The USA embassy in Uzbekistan opened one such center last March in Karshi. Plans are in place to set up six more in the country, with more than \$860,000 (9.3 billion UZS) earmarked for the initiative.

The United States is also helping Uzbek teachers and students by providing textbooks for schools. The textbooks, which were developed by Cambridge University Press are valued at \$10million (108.4 billion UZS), will support the teaching of information and communications technology (ICT) for grades 5 to 11 and English as foreign language for grades 1 to 11. USAID

is also training and mentoring more than 1,000 English and ICT teachers on using the new textbooks and teacher guides and on mastering learner-centered teaching strategies.

To conclude, we cannot imagine our modern life without learning foreign languages such as English. It helps us know about other countries culture as well as main purpose of communication. I believe that it leads to bright future all our Uzbek youngsters.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 19.05.2021 No. PQ-5117 <https://lex.uz/docs/-5426736>;
2. https://central.asia-news.com/en_GB/articles/cnmi_ca/features/2022/01/06/feature-02.
3. Abbasova, N. K. (2020). O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA OLMOSHLARNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 472-476)
4. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). ХОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА ҚЎШМА ГАПЛАР ТАВСИФИ, ТАСНИФИ ВА МЕТАТИЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(В6), 560-564.
5. Maxammadjonova, S. H. (2022). THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM AND THE THEORY OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN IT. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(4), 129-133.
6. Aliyeva, N. (2021). СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФРАЗЕМ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ, РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 3(8).
7. Омонова, М. К., & Нурматова, М. М. (2017). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРАВИЛЬНОСТЬ В ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ В ПИСЬМЕ. *Ученый XXI века*, 93.
8. Bazarova, D. (2022). VARIABILITY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS. *Science and innovation*, 1(В7), 483-486.
9. Kakharov, K., & Azizov, Y. (2022). Mnemonics Techniques for Teaching English Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 385-387.
10. Кахаров, Қ., & Абдусаломова, Г. (2022). ЧЕТ ТИЛИ ЎРГАНИШДА АХБОРОТ ВОСИТАЛАРИНИНГ РОЛИ. *ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(10), 152-155.
11. Dushatova, S. (2022). EVFEMIZM TUSHUNCHASI TAHLILI. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(3), 159-163.
12. Soxibovna, M. G. (2022, August). THE ROLE OF LINVOCULTUREME IN THE STUDY OF NATIONAL AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF SPEECH UNITS. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 48-52).
13. Yuzboy ogli, R. A. (2022, April). ANGLIYA ELCHISI ALEKSANDR BYORNSNING BUXOROGA SAYOHATI TAFSILOTLARI. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 176-177).
14. Yuzboy o'g'li, R. A. (2022). ANTONY JENKINSON'S VISIT TO THE KHANATE OF BUKHARA AND THE LEADING ROLE OF THE KHANATE OF BUKHARA IN TRADE RELATIONS BETWEEN INDIA AND RUSSIA. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 19(1), 174-177.

15. Kakharova, S. (2022). Speech as a Tool of Pedagogical Activity of the Teachers. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 61-64.
16. Жахонгиров, Б. Б. (2016). НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЕ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО УЗБЕКИСТАНА С ЗАРУБЕЖНЫМИ СТРАНАМИ. *Наука и образование: проблемы и тенденции развития*, (1), 18-20.
17. Soxibovna, M. G. THE ROLE OF LINGUVOCULARY IN THE STUDY OF NATIONAL AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF SPEECH UNITS.
18. Olimovna, S. N. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ TASHKILOTLARIDA HAR BIR YOSH GURUHIDA TEVARAK ATROFNI IDROK ETISHNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Results of National Scientific Research*, 1(1), 115-119.
19. Ubaydullaeva, D., & Yuldasheva, Z. (2020). POLYSEMY IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 234-235).